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D2.15

Final Federation Board Specification

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Abstract	This deliverable is the final Federation Board deliverable. It evaluates the principles and policies of the Federation Board work within Fed4FIRE and also discusses the Federation Board's position within the follow-on project, Fed4FIRE+, as well as making recommendations to the follow-on project.
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	PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)	
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

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1 Introduction

This document is the final deliverable in the “Federation Board” series for Fed4FIRE. The deliverable’s original purpose was to provide an evaluation of the Federation Board (also referred to as “FB”) structure and policies set out in previous Federation Board deliverables, but a major change in the status of the Fed4FIRE federation has dictated that this scope be expanded somewhat. Since the release of D2.14, the Fed4FIRE federation’s future has been secured in the medium term with the award of the EC H2020 grant for “Fed4FIRE+”, a new project to operate and extend the Fed4FIRE federation. Therefore, any assessment and evaluation of the Federation Board’s composition, position and principles must be within the context of this new funding and project structure, as this is the future of the Fed4FIRE federation, and this is the new focus of this deliverable.

The Federation Board is responsible for steering the operational federation. It represents the interests of the key stakeholders in the federation, that is, the testbeds and the federator, and this representation determines the composition of the board. The Federation Board determines policies regarding key principles of the federation (described in D2.14), including performance indicators, the federation’s operational model, eligibility, resource management, terms and conditions, services the federator offers, communication and marketing, and the future direction of the federation.

Fed4FIRE+ has a task dedicated to federation governance (Task 2.3: Federation Board), which has the following objectives (from the Fed4FIRE+ description of work):

- *Decide upon the direction and principles of the federation,*
- *Define the technical and legal requirements needed for a testbed to join the infrastructure community,*
- *Evaluate what demand-driven extensions are needed*
- *Determine topics which need to be addressed in the Fed4FIRE+ open calls for experimentation.*

The Federation Board’s purpose and policies have been proposed within Fed4FIRE, and can serve as a baseline for those within Fed4FIRE+. Whilst the policies and federation structure proposed within Fed4FIRE cannot be mandated as policy for Fed4FIRE+, they can serve as recommendations to be adopted and adapted as necessary within Fed4FIRE+.

This deliverable firstly examines the position of the FB within the new project’s structure, and then it make recommendations as to the board’s membership and election. These are developed and updated from the previous FB deliverable in the light of the new project. The responsibilities of the FB are discussed next, with an assessment of the policies from previous FB and sustainability deliverables. Finally conclusions are drawn and recommendations for the FB into the next project are made.

2 Federation Board's Position within Fed4FIRE+

The Fed4FIRE+ Description of work stipulates that the functions of the Federation Board Task (T2.3) are the following.

Set-up and support the Federation Board, a policy-making body whose objective is to steer the federation. This board will decide upon:

- *the direction and principles of the federation,*
- *will define the technical and legal requirements needed for a testbed to join the infrastructure community,*
- *will evaluate what demand-driven extensions are needed and*
- *will issue topics which need to be addressed in upcoming calls to be set up by WP5. [Fed4FIRE+ Description of Work]*

From these objectives, the interactions between the Federation Board and other project elements can be determined. Figure 1 shows the Federation Board's interactions within the workpackages and tasks of the Fed4FIRE+ project.

Figure 1: Federation Board Interactions

It can be seen that the main interactions are within WP2, which is to be expected because WP2 is concerned with the federation's Federator, the entity responsible for the running of the

federation. WP2 also contains tasks that provide interfaces to other workpackages, and these are shown in the figure.

The FB will coexist with the project management, but the project's management and the FB cover two different concerns: the project management is (obviously) concerned with the delivery of the Fed4FIRE+ project, and the FB is concerned with the steering and governance of the federation as it operates.

The comparison between the organisational structures of the operational federation and the Fed4FIRE+ project is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Operational Federation and Fed4FIRE+ Project Structure

The FB must represent the interests of the key stakeholders of the operational federation. These are the Testbeds and the Federator, because these two actor types form the operational federation who serve its “customers”, the experimenters.

The project has a standard structure, where the major decision-making body is the General Assembly, representing all partners in the project. The Executive Committee is a delegated management body comprising the project management plus workpackage leaders.

The operational federation will run within the overall remit of the Fed4FIRE+ project during the project's lifetime, but given that the project aims for a sustainable federation, the project management and federation governance should be kept separate. During the course of the project, the relationship between the project's management and governance of the operational federation must be determined: it is unclear at this stage how the Federation Board will fit into the project's management structure. Clearly, the Federation Board needs to have authority if it is to be effective, and therefore it is recommended that the Federation Board's influence and relationship with the Fed4FIRE+ project's management structure is clarified before month 3 of the project.

Even though the operational federation and the project share funding under the umbrella of the project, the project and the operational federation may have different objectives, and any conflicts or tensions between the two concerns will have to be managed by negotiation between the Federation Board and the project's Executive Committee. Conflict resolution

principles must be jointly defined by the project management and federation governance, and the general principle to be followed is that the objectives of the operational federation and the project may be different, but they must not conflict or be contradictory.

3 Federation Board Membership

3.1 Board Size & Structure

The membership of the Federation Board will need to be determined under the remit of the new project. Research suggests that in general the size of a board of directors should not be excessive, and 5-7 members is most likely to be optimal¹, so this assessment will assume an initial proposal of 6 members of the Federation Board.

It is recommended that a senior person within the project partner organisation hosting the Federator be a board member. This is because the Federator is responsible for managing the federation and therefore will be responsible for executing the decisions and policies of the Federation Board. This is analogous to the Chief Executive Officer of a company having a seat on the company's board of directors. At this point it is not clear which organisation in the new project will actually operate the federator, so this needs to be determined at an early stage of the project.

There must not be more than one member of the same organisation on the FB. The purpose of this limit is to avoid imbalances of power or influence from a single organisation within the governance of the operational federation.

Given all the above, the overall structure of the FB is recommended to be:

- 1 Federator
- 1 External board member
- 4 Testbed owners

3.2 Appointment Process & Tenure

Board members should be appointed by ballot, with each testbed having one vote. Some organisations within the Fed4FIRE+ project have more than one testbed, and one vote per testbed means that the organisations with the largest stake in the federation have the greatest say in appointment of the federation's governing body. The federation must maintain an up-to-date register of testbeds that provide resources to the federation at any given time, and this determines the electorate for appointing FB members.

In many traditional-style company boards of directors, there is an external, independent director, to provide a different perspective than the other board members, which are often tightly bound up with the entity governed by the board. Therefore it is recommended that the board have one board member from outside the federation, and an external board member could be a senior person from a related federation, e.g. GENI.

Nominations for membership can be made initially by any member of the Fed4FIRE+ General Assembly, and must be seconded by another organisation within the GA. An organisation may nominate a member of their own staff. Once a nomination and a second has occurred, a ballot of testbeds can be conducted at a suitable time. In the case of a single nomination for a board position, the ballot's purpose is to determine whether the nominee is appointed (or vetoed). It

¹ <http://cyruswhite.com/nonprofit-boards-smaller-is-better/>

is recommended that the ballot be secret, as testbeds may not wish to declare how they have voted. In the event that the number of votes is tied, FB will decide between the tied candidates through an open ballot within itself. In the event of a tied vote within the FB, it is suggested that the external board member has the casting vote, so as to avoid conflicts of interest within the federation.

Any board member who leaves a federation partner organisation (i.e. all but the external board member) will automatically leave the FB at the time they leave the partner organisation. This will result in an empty space in the FB, and there will need to be a new election to fill the space in the board. This election should be within 3 months of the leaving date of the previous board member.

It has been recommended in D2.14 that fixed-tenure positions on the board be employed, to avoid stagnation and complacency within the FB. It is suggested that fixed tenures are employed, with the tenure expiry triggering election of a new board member, but also that existing board members can be eligible for re-election once their tenure time expires.

Removal of a board member for non-performance can follow a similar process to appointments: any federation partner can nominate removal of a board member, and this must be seconded by another partner. This necessarily must be secret, but verification that the nomination and second are genuine needs to be performed by the project's Executive Committee members. Voting should be performed in a secret ballot by testbed owners in the same manner as for appointment, but the question here is whether they agree with the removal of a board member rather than the appointment of one.

4 Responsibilities of the Federation Board

The FB's main responsibilities are to determine the principles of the federation, steer direction for the federation, and to create policy for the federation's operation.

To determine the direction for the federation, firstly the core purpose of the federation must be defined, and hence a mission statement for the federation is needed. To monitor and evaluate the performance of the federation against its key objectives, Performance Indicators (PIs) are required that determine metrics and targets of key aspects of performance. As a result of this, a large part of the FB's work is in monitoring and assessing the federation's performance against the PI metrics, analysing and making recommendations about how the federation can improve its performance.

The FB is also responsible for deciding on policies, which determine the rules and processes for the operational federation. These have been determined in detail in D2.14, and are assessed here to evaluate whether the new situation of the Fed4FIRE+ follow on project require any changes to them.

4.1 Determine a Mission Statement for the Federation

The FB should determine a mission statement for the federation, to provide a concise reference point describing the federation's reason to be. According to Bart², a mission statement for an organisation should contain three key elements:

- The key market (beneficiaries) of the organisation's activities
- The contribution of the organisation
- The unique selling point of the organisation.

The federation is the organisation that is the subject of the mission statement, and its beneficiaries are future experimenters in Europe.

The contribution of the federation is to support and promote the European acquisition of knowledge and development of technology in the Future Internet by providing access to testing facilities to assist European experimenters in the Future Internet.

The distinction of the federation is that it provides easy and seamless access to testbeds of many different types for experimenters, within the same experiment if required, and through this, innovative experiments are facilitated.

Given the above, a draft mission statement for the federation could be:

The Fed4FIRE federation's purpose is to support and promote European acquisition of knowledge and development of technology in the Future Internet by providing easy and seamless access to many different types of testing facilities together with associated support services, in order to assist European Future Internet experimenters.

² Bart, Christopher (2015). "Sex, Lies and Mission Statements".

http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=716542. Retrieved 24 Nov 2016.

4.2 Determine the Future Direction for the Federation

The FB needs to steer the federation, mainly to ensure that the federation continues to provide relevant and useful experimental facilities and support services at an adequate level of quality. The recommended approach for evaluating performance is using Performance Indicators (PIs). Different types of PI have been suggested in previous deliverables, and are discussed further next, along with a discussion regarding how to monitor them.

4.2.1 Determination & Assessment of Performance Indicators

To assist with the evaluation of performance, and to highlight where the federation needs to change, it is recommended that the FB determines metrics to provide information on performance of the federation compared against targets. These can be based on the Performance Indicators (PIs) in D2.14. These are discussed below in broad categories, with comments based on lessons learned since D2.14 was written. For Fed4FIRE+, the FB needs to determine which of these performance indicators are important, to determine any additional PIs needed, and what the desired targets are for each PI. This will define the overall objectives of the federation in terms that should be easy to measure and assess performance against.

Number of experiments and experimenters

The number of experiments represents the critical measure of how successful the federation is. It determines the amount of “business” the federation is doing, and how well it is serving its “customers” (the experimenters).

In general the experiment numbers should be increasing over time if the federation is successful. The experiments break down into two major categories in terms of their funding:

- Experiments that are funded by the federation or the project. This means that the federation’s resources are provided free of charge, and also that the experimenter’s time is paid for (usually through the mechanism of open calls). These experiments may make valuable contributions to the federation in terms of generating new requirements.
- Experiments that are funded by the experimenters themselves. In general this means that the federation’s resources are provided free of charge but the experimenters are not paid for their time (the so-called “open access” model). This type of experiment is needed to achieve sustainability for the federation because it means that the experimenters see significant value in the resources and services provided by the federation – enough value to warrant their investment of time in the experiment.

There must be a balance between these two types of experimenters if the federation is to be successful, with significant number of self-funded experimenters if the federation is also to be sustainable beyond the end of the new project.

In addition to the number of experiments, the number of distinct experimenters is also important. The federation should be attracting new users, and so the number of new experimenters should also be increasing over time, in addition to existing experimenters coming back for new experiments.

Hence the PIs for experiments and experimenters are:

- Overall number of experiments

- Number of experiments where the experimenters' time is funded by the project
- Number of experiments where the experimenters' time is funded by themselves
- Ratio of federation-funded vs self-funded experimenters
- Number of distinct experimenters

Number & relevance of testbeds

As with the numbers of experimenters, the number of testbeds should be in general increasing overall if the federation is successful. This is akin to the expansion of a successful business by acquiring additional capacity or diversifying.

A critical performance indicator is that the testbeds should be relevant to the needs of the end users, so PIs must be determined to monitor the utilisation of the testbeds to check which ones are being used, and which are not. The units of utilisation will need to be determined by the federation, and if they are different (e.g. CPU hours vs bandwidth), how they may be compared. In this comparison, a key factor is the relationship between the resource offered by a testbed to the federation and the amount taken up by experimenters – it may be that simple percentage utilisation is adequate across all testbeds, but this needs to be investigated in the new project.

The number of testbeds that offer “advanced federation” (as defined by Fed4FIRE) is an important PI. These are the most desirable type of federated testbeds because they are fully compliant with the standards and integrated with the tools of the federation, and as a result are easier to use by experimenters.

An important performance indicator for testbeds is to determine the new types of resource that are in demand by experimenters, but are not being currently provided. This is cannot be measured by monitoring the usage of testbeds in the federation, but by other methods, e.g. surveying existing experimenters and looking at trends in the related disciplines outside the federation.

Hence PIs for testbeds are:

- Overall number of testbeds
 - Number of “advanced federation” testbeds compared to simpler forms of federation
- Number of experiments that are delayed due to lack of testbed resource
 - Which resource is in demand but under-provided?
- Testbeds that are under-utilised
 - Types of resources they provide
- Testbeds that have high utilisation
 - Types of resources they provide
- Demand for new resources
 - E.g. Survey experiment community for new types of resources desired

Federator Effectiveness

These PIs measure whether the services provided by the federator are effective – e.g. which services are most used and which are less used. In the case of under-utilised services, the reason why the service in question is not popular needs to be determined.

The PIs are:

- Number of services provided by federation for experimenters
 - Which services are utilised most
 - Which services are utilised least & why
- Number of services provided by federation for testbeds
 - Which services are utilised most
 - Which services are utilised least & why

Marketing & community building effectiveness

These PIs measure the effectiveness of the “marketing” of the federation, and how successful the federation is in building a community in and around the federation. This is chiefly directed at recruiting new experimenters and testbeds, so as to build this community.

The PIs are:

- Number of new experimenters per type of recruitment drive
 - E.g. as a result of summer schools or conferences organised by the project / federation
 - Compare against cost of campaign
- Number of new testbeds per type of recruitment drive
 - Compare against cost of campaign

4.2.2 Gathering and Analysing Experimenter Feedback & Preferences

In order to determine the current demand for the federation, to determine “customer satisfaction” and in part to determine future demand, a major aspect of the FB’s work involves monitoring and analysing the needs and satisfaction of the target “customers” of the federation, the experimenters.

This monitoring can take many forms and will provide the means to answer many different types of question regarding how well the federation is serving its users. The monitoring provides intelligence that can be analysed within the FB so that it can advise the testbeds on new types of resources they might want to provide, to help predict resource demand, and to provide input to the open calls for testbed developments and funded experimentation.

Some monitoring mechanisms are proposed in the Fed4FIRE+ description of work:

- Fed4FIRE+ proposes conferences for the Future Internet community, so these are a good way of getting feedback from the community about what is required by it. It is recommended that surveys and other means of gathering feedback about the needs of the community are conducted at these events.
- Fed4FIRE+ will use a mechanism of open calls for experiments, and the types of experiment and the resources needed for them will provide indication of the demand for the types of resources already provided in the federation. User surveys are required as part of the funding scheme for experiments in the open calls, and these should include a section on the type of resources that are not yet provided by the federation.

4.3 Starting Point Policies

This section considers the policies from D2.10 (Final Sustainability Plan) and D2.14 (Federation Board Release Candidate) in the light of the experience gained within the final

year of Fed4FIRE and in the context of Fed4FIRE+, making recommendations for updates to the policies from the previous deliverable where it is deemed necessary.

4.3.1 Operational Model of the Federation

D2.10 has recommended the “one-stop shop” FitSM model³ as the chosen operational model. This is where the federator takes charge of matching resources in testbeds with the experimenter’s requirements and experiment setup, but stops short of actually running the experiment on behalf of the experimenter.

This is a reasonable compromise between the federator adding value to the experimenter (the experimenter does not have to discover and set up the resources) and giving the experimenter control over their experiment (once the resources are setup, the experimenter can e.g. SSH into them and run their experiment).

It remains to be seen whether other models, which provide less encapsulation by the federator (e.g. the experimenter does more of the resource allocation or setup), or more encapsulation by the federator (e.g. the federator takes entire control of the experiment) are appropriate, and the FB simply needs to analyse the feedback from experimenters to determine whether the operational model is the right one, and to provide recommendations and reasoning to adopt an alternative or additional operational model.

4.3.2 Eligibility Requirements

D2.14 has advocated as wide acceptability for experimenters and testbeds as possible, and there is no reason to change this for the new project or the continuing federation. It is a stated aim to increase the numbers of experimenters and testbeds, and as long as the new applicants undertake to be law-abiding and comply with the terms and conditions of the federation, they should be permitted to join. In addition to compliance with terms and conditions, testbeds need to be technically compliant. There are levels of compliance specified in Fed4FIRE, and the lowest level of compliance is simple to achieve for testbeds, so this is not a significant barrier.

4.3.3 Resource Management

D2.14 states that testbeds should provide small amounts of resource to allow for demos and users’ testing of the testbed, and any more resource provided by the testbed is at the discretion of the testbed. The testbeds may optionally offer SLAs to provide experimenters with guarantees on the resources they provide.

There is no reason to change any of this for the new project, as all the policies here are in the best interests of the federation, and if a testbed wishes to gain a good reputation within the federation, they will provide adequate resource to serve the experimenters that wish to use the testbed. The federation is a good source of users for testbeds, which validates their existence, so testbeds should have a vested interest in providing adequate resources to the federation. If a testbed wishes to offer SLAs, this is seen as an enhanced service and evidence of their commitment to experimenters and the federation.

³ <http://fitsm.itemo.org/>

4.3.4 Services the Federator offers

D2.10 states that towards the experimenter, the federator offers:

- Identity management for single sign-on, allowing the experimenter easy access to all testbeds within the federation.
- A portal for discovery of relevant testbeds.
- Tools for resource reservation at testbeds.
- Documentation on how to use the federation.
- First level support to help experimenters address problems within the federation.
- SLA management, enabling experimenters to receive guarantees on resources offered by the federation.

Towards the testbeds, the federator offers:

- An API that allows testbeds to become technically compliant with the federation.
- Promotion of the testbeds within the federation, providing access to a greater number of potential experimenters than the testbed has access to without.
- If the testbeds want it, automatic allocation of resources to experimenters.
- SLA management, enabling testbeds to offer guarantees on resources provided by them.

All these are perfectly reasonable and should continue.

One point of concern is how much effort is required by the testbeds to become “advanced level” technically compliant with the federation. This is a potentially significant barrier to new testbeds joining the federation, so the federator needs to concentrate on enhancing the tools and services to simplify this for testbeds. The acid test will be if a testbed joins the federation at their own cost – i.e. their effort to join the federation at advanced level is not funded by the federation. This will be evidence that the cost to join the federation is acceptably low, and the benefits of federation membership are seen to warrant the cost.

4.3.5 Communications and Marketing

D2.14 covers the communication and marketing of the federation with specific policies separately addressing recruitment of experimenters and testbeds. A major point of principle is that the communications and marketing performed by the federation is provided as a service to the federation members, i.e. the federation management promotes the federation, which benefits all its members. As an example of this, the testbeds benefit from the federation’s promotion via greater numbers of experimenters coming to experiment – in effect, the federation is a sales channel for the testbeds. A related point of principle is that the federation can benefit from the contacts that the individual members have already, and also whatever promotion they do.

The different channels and targets employed so far in Fed4FIRE, e.g. the website, attendance at high profile events, community events like summer schools and open calls for funded experiments all should continue into the new project. The consortium has experience in these, and they have provided adequate returns on the time invested. The open calls in particular have been successful – each call has always been over-subscribed, and they provide a

mechanism for experimenters to find out what the federation has to offer at zero cost (even the experimenters' time is paid for in most open calls).

Some marketing policy is allied to market analysis. Market analysis determines what is needed by the customer base, and if there are gaps, they will be highlighted as candidates to be evaluated for future federation operations. This can translate into new opportunities for testbeds, i.e. new resources they could provide. Here the federation's market analysis can be communicated to candidate testbeds, either within the federation or outside the federation, as either an added value service or an opportunity respectively.

It is not clear from the Fed4FIRE+ description of work how marketing of the federation will be performed, or indeed who will be responsible for marketing strategy. Therefore it is recommended that it be decided who will be responsible for the Fed4FIRE+ marketing strategy, and that an overall marketing strategy / plan with the overall objective of recruiting experimenters and testbeds be created at an early stage within the project. This should be consistent with the overall objectives of the federation and contain what the objectives of the federation's marketing are, how the marketing will be done, and who will do it.

4.3.6 Future Direction for the Federation

This has been covered in detail in a separate section previously.

4.3.7 Funding for Federation Stakeholders

D2.10 has covered funding models and opportunities, and part of this work was included in the project proposal for Fed4FIRE+, as it was understood that the major source of funding for a federation supporting experimentation into the Future Internet would be from public investment at an international level – no individual profit-making private organisation is likely to fund such a venture, since the nature of experimentation is uncertain, with consequent uncertainty on a return on the investment. D2.10 advocates that any business model chosen should not hamper eligibility for funding schemes – this is obviously a sensible policy, as it is important to keep all funding options open.

Clearly, the question of how the federation will be funded beyond the end of Fed4FIRE+ is a crucial question for the new project, and one which will need to be investigated during the course of the project.

4.3.8 Terms and Conditions

D2.14 has proposed sets of terms and conditions for experimenters and testbeds joining the federation. These are fairly standard, and cover aspects such as lawful and ethical behaviour in the federation, limitation of liability, non-intrusive behaviour, acceptance and enforcement of the terms and conditions, maintenance of testbeds, compliance with audit procedures, and responsibility for third parties. None of these clauses are particularly controversial, oppressive or onerous, so no changes are recommended.

5 Conclusions & Recommendations

This deliverable has provided commentary for the Fed4FIRE Federation Board work at the end of the Fed4FIRE project, and especially in the light of Fed4FIRE's continuation project, Fed4FIRE+.

The main conclusion of this deliverable regards the FB's main responsibilities. These are to determine direction for the federation, and to create policy for the federation's operation, all consistent with the mission statement of the federation, which is essentially to continue to provide useful and relevant experimentation resources to the Future Internet research community.

An initial set of Performance Indicators have been determined and these provide criteria against which the federation's performance can be measured, and the FB's responsibility is to analyse this performance and to determine any actions necessary to improve performance. This includes research for new directions, resources and services that keep the federation relevant to its target community of users.

This deliverable has made recommendations for the new project, Fed4FIRE+, and these represent the experience gained within Fed4FIRE. We cannot mandate that Fed4FIRE+ follow these recommendations, but they are made so that Fed4FIRE+ can benefit from the experience of Fed4FIRE. The major recommendations for Fed4FIRE+ are summarised as follows.

- Fed4FIRE+ T2.3 (Federation Board) should determine the members of the initial Federation Board before month 3 of the new project. It is recommended that the board consist of 5-7 members: of which, one is the federator, another is external to the federation, and the remainder are testbed owners. An appointment procedure for FB members via ballot has been proposed, and it is recommended that this be taken up, but if not, an alternative or revised procedure needs to be determined before the members are appointed – meaning within the first 3 months of the project.
- Before month 3 of the project, the project's General Assembly should decide which organisation in the Fed4FIRE+ consortium will be the federator, who manages and enables the operational federation.
- The Fed4FIRE+ project management, General Assembly and Executive Committee together with Fed4FIRE+ Task 2.3 should determine the relationship between the Fed4FIRE+ FB and the project's management structure before month 3 of the project. Aims and objectives of the project management and the federation operational management must not be contradictory.
- The Federation Board should evaluate the Performance Indicators (PIs) described in D2.14 and this deliverable, adding and adjusting where necessary to determine the set of PIs for the operational Fed4FIRE+ federation. This will include determining utilisation metrics for federation resources. The FB needs to periodically monitor and assess measurements against these metrics to determine the performance of the federation. The output of this exercise can inform steering for the future direction of the federation.

- The Federation Board should conduct market analysis to assist with the federation's future direction. This includes analysis of the PIs described above, but also should include surveys of the experimenters for their satisfaction with the federation, as well as feedback on services or resources that the federation does not currently provide, but should.
- The Fed4FIRE+ project should determine an overall marketing strategy before month 3 of the project with the overall objective of recruiting experimenters and testbeds to the federation. This should contain what the objectives of the federation's marketing are, how the marketing and analysis will be done, and who will do it. It is up to the project's partners as to who is responsible for this strategy (e.g. dissemination tasks), but the strategy needs to be in line with the objectives and principles of the federation, so the FB needs to have significant input into this strategy.